

Mapping Literature Landscapes with Data-Driven Discovery: A Case Study on MOEA/D

Anonymous authors

APPENDIX A GPT PROMPTS

➤ Prompt for Affiliation Wrangling

“Imagine this scenario: You are given with a list of academic institutions:

[DOCUMENTS]

Your task is to identify institutions that appear with multiple spellings or abbreviations but actually refer to the same entity, and suggest a standardized name for them in this format:

[RAW NAME] -> [STANDARDIZED NAME]

Examples:

[Examples]”

➤ Prompt for Venue Wrangling

“Imagine this scenario: You are given with a list of academic venues:

[DOCUMENTS]

Your task is to identify venues that appear with multiple spellings or abbreviations but actually refer to the same entity, and suggest a standardized name for them in this format:

[RAW NAME] -> [STANDARDIZED NAME]

Examples:

[Examples]”

➤ Prompt for Citation Intent Classification

“Given the citation statement:

[CITATION STATEMENT]

Which of the following options is the most appropriate way to categorize #[CITATION TAG] according to the author’s reasoning for citing it?

[CATEGORIES WITH DESCRIPTIONS]

Examples:

[Examples]”

➤ Prompt for Topic Representation

“This is a list of paper titles and abstracts:

[SAMPLE PAPER CONTENTS]

Each collection of papers describe a certain specific research topic within (decomposition-based) evolutionary multi-objective optimization. After each collection of papers, the name of the topic they represent is mentioned as a short-highly-descriptive title, and description of the topic is a concise highlighting summary with 1-2 sentence. The description should only offers a bird-view on the essence of the topics (e.g., those related to the keywords). For topics focused on applications, the description should include what are the conflicting objectives, and what are the optimization variables.

Examples:

[Examples]”

➤ Prompt for Keyword Extraction

Agent 1 (Extraction)

“Imagine this scenario: You are given the abstract of a paper in evolutionary multi-objective optimization (EMO):

[ABSTRACT]

Your task is to extract a comprehensive candidate list of EMO-related keywords that represent the core methods, concepts, tasks, benchmarks, and application context discussed in the abstract. The extracted keywords are not limited to a fixed category list. They can include algorithm names and variants, optimization paradigms, operators, indicators/metrics, benchmark suites/problems, theoretical concepts, and domain/application terms whenever they are central to the paper.

Return the result as a comma-separated candidate list only.

Examples:

Input Abstract: [EXAMPLE ABSTRACT]

Candidate Keywords: [EXAMPLE CANDIDATES]”

Agent 2 (Verification)

“Imagine this scenario: You are given the same paper abstract and a candidate keyword list generated by another LLM:

[ABSTRACT]

[CANDIDATE KEYWORDS FROM AGENT 1]

Your task is to verify whether the candidate list is complete and correct for EMO keyword extraction. Specifically, check that: (a) no important EMO-relevant keyword present in the abstract is missing, and (b) every keyword in the candidate list is explicitly grounded in the abstract and relevant to EMO.

If the candidate list is fully correct, output the original candidate list unchanged. Otherwise, output a revised comma-separated list that fixes omissions and removes invalid terms.

Return only one final comma-separated list.

Examples:

Input Abstract: [EXAMPLE ABSTRACT]

Input Candidates: [EXAMPLE CANDIDATES]

Final Output: [EXAMPLE FINAL KEYWORDS]"

● Sample Input/Output for Keyword Extraction

Sample Input:

Abstract: Achieving balance between convergence and diversity is a key issue in evolutionary multiobjective optimization. Most existing methodologies, which have demonstrated their niche on various practical problems involving two and three objectives, face significant challenges in many-objective optimization. This paper suggests a unified paradigm, which combines dominance- and decomposition-based approaches, for many-objective optimization. Our major purpose is to exploit the merits of both dominance- and decomposition-based approaches to balance the convergence and diversity of the evolutionary process. The performance of our proposed method is validated and compared with four state-of-the-art algorithms on a number of unconstrained benchmark problems with up to 15 objectives. Empirical results fully demonstrate the superiority of our proposed method on all considered test instances. In addition, we extend this method to solve constrained problems having a large number of objectives. Compared to two other recently proposed constrained optimizers, our proposed method shows highly competitive performance on all the constrained optimization problems.

Agent 1 Output (Candidate Keywords):

convergence, diversity, evolutionary multiobjective optimization, many-objective optimization, dominance-based approach, decomposition-based approach, unconstrained benchmark problems, constrained optimization, constrained optimizers.

Agent 2 Output (Verified Keywords):

convergence, diversity, evolutionary multiobjective optimization, many-objective optimization, dominance-based approach, decomposition-based approach, unconstrained benchmark problems, constrained optimization.

● Sample Input/Output for Affiliation Wrangling

Sample Input:

HKUST; Hong Kong University of Science and Technology; The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology; Michigan State Univ.; Michigan State University

Sample Output:

HKUST -> The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology
 Hong Kong University of Science and Technology -> The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology
 Michigan State Univ. -> Michigan State University

● Sample Input/Output for Venue Wrangling

Sample Input:

IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation; IEEE Trans. on Evolutionary Computation; TEVC; GECCO '19: Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference; GECCO

Sample Output:

IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation -> IEEE Trans. Evol. Comput.
 IEEE Trans. on Evolutionary Computation -> IEEE Trans. Evol. Comput.
 GECCO '19: Proceedings of the Genetic and Evolutionary Computation Conference -> GECCO

● Sample Input/Output for Citation Intent Classification

Sample Input:

Citation statement: "We use the decomposition strategy of MOEA/D [12] as the baseline framework and compare our selection operator against it."

Citation tag: #12

Candidate categories: Background, Method, Extension, Comparison

Sample Output:

Method

APPENDIX B
ADDITIONAL DETAILS

- **Densification Power Law:** Introduced by Leskovec et al. (2005), this law describes how real-world networks evolve. It states that as a network grows, the number of edges $E(t)$ (citations) grows faster than the number of nodes $N(t)$ (papers), following a power-law relationship $E(t) \propto N(t)^\alpha$. It is used to measure the growth dynamics of a community. An exponent $\alpha > 1$ (like our 1.41) is interpreted as the network becoming increasingly dense over time: newer papers tend to introduce more connections (citations) on average than older ones, indicating a highly active and rapidly interconnecting research field.
- **CD Index:** The consolidation/disruption index (Funk & Owen-Smith, 2017) measures whether a paper establishes a new paradigm (disruptive) or builds upon existing knowledge (consolidating). For a focal paper p , it is computed as $CD_p = (n_F - n_B)/(n_F + n_B + n_R)$, where: 1) n_F is the number of papers citing p but *none* of p 's references (highlighting disruption, as subsequent research focuses entirely on p); 2) n_B is the number of papers citing both p and at least one of its references (highlighting consolidation); and 3) n_R is the number of papers citing p 's references but *not* p . The resulting score ranges from -1 (fully consolidating) to 1 (fully disruptive).
- **Ranking Method:** Proposed by Wang et al. (2013), this is a heterogeneous graph-based ranking algorithm (akin to an advanced PageRank). Rather than relying solely on citation counts, it computes a paper's influence by simultaneously factoring in: (1) the influence of citing papers, (2) the authority of authors, and (3) the prestige of the publication venue. Furthermore, it incorporates a time-decay penalty to adjust for publication age, which ensures that newer, high-impact papers are fairly compared against older, established works that naturally had more time to accumulate citations.

APPENDIX C
ESSENTIAL PUBLICATIONS IN THE MOEA/D LANDSCAPE (MAIN PATH ANALYSIS)

TABLE A1
ESSENTIAL PUBLICATIONS IN THE MOEA/D LANDSCAPE.

ID	Title	Venue	Year
Q. Zhang 2007	MOEA/D: A Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithm Based on Decomposition	TEVC	2007
Q. Zhang 2009	The performance of a new version of MOEA/D on CEC09 unconstrained MOP test instances	CEC	2009
H. Li 2009	Multiobjective Optimization Problems With Complicated Pareto Sets, MOEA/D and NSGA-II	TEVC	2009
H. Ishibuchi 2009a	Adaptation of Scalarizing Functions in MOEA/D: An Adaptive Scalarizing Function-Based Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithm	EMO	2009
H. Ishibuchi 2009b	Evolutionary many-objective optimization by NSGA-II and MOEA/D with large populations	SMC	2009
Q. Zhang 2010	Expensive Multiobjective Optimization by MOEA/D With Gaussian Process Model	TEVC	2010
H. Ishibuchi 2010b	Simultaneous use of different scalarizing functions in MOEA/D	GECCO	2010
H. Ishibuchi 2010a	Many-Objective Test Problems to Visually Examine the Behavior of Multiobjective Evolution in a Decision Space	PPSN	2010
H. Li 2011	An Adaptive Evolutionary Multi-Objective Approach Based on Simulated Annealing	ECJ	2011
YY Tan 2012	A modification to MOEA/D-DE for multiobjective optimization problems with complicated Pareto sets	Info. Sci.	2012
Y. Wang 2012	A regularity model-based multiobjective estimation of distribution algorithm with reducing redundant cluster operator	Appl. Soft. Comput.	2012
S-Z Zhao 2012	Decomposition-Based Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithm With an Ensemble of Neighborhood Sizes	TEVC	2012
S. Yang 2013	A Grid-Based Evolutionary Algorithm for Many-Objective Optimization	TEVC	2013
R. Wang 2013	Preference-Inspired Coevolutionary Algorithms for Many-Objective Optimization	TEVC	2013
K. Sindhya 2013	A Hybrid Framework for Evolutionary Multi-Objective Optimization	TEVC	2013
DK Saxena 2013	Objective Reduction in Many-Objective Optimization: Linear and Nonlinear Algorithms	TEVC	2013
Z. He 2014	Fuzzy-Based Pareto Optimality for Many-Objective Evolutionary Algorithms	TEVC	2014
Y. Qi 2014	MOEA/D with Adaptive Weight Adjustment	ECJ	2014
M. Li 2014	Shift-Based Density Estimation for Pareto-Based Algorithms in Many-Objective Optimization	TEVC	2014
K. Li 2014a	Adaptive Operator Selection With Bandits for a Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithm Based on Decomposition	TEVC	2014
K. Li 2014b	Stable Matching-Based Selection in Evolutionary Multiobjective Optimization	TEVC	2014
K. Deb 2014	An Evolutionary Many-Objective Optimization Algorithm Using Reference-Point-Based Nondominated Sorting Approach, Part I: Solving Problems With Box Constraints	TEVC	2014
H. Jain 2014	An Evolutionary Many-Objective Optimization Algorithm Using Reference-Point Based Nondominated Sorting Approach, Part II: Handling Constraints and Extending to an Adaptive Approach	TEVC	2014
H-L Liu 2014	Decomposition of a Multiobjective Optimization Problem Into a Number of Simple Multiobjective Subproblems	TEVC	2014
Gary G. Yen 2014	Performance Metric Ensemble for Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithms	TEVC	2014
X. Zhang 2015	A Knee Point-Driven Evolutionary Algorithm for Many-Objective Optimization	TEVC	2015
X. Cai 2015	An External Archive Guided Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithm Based on Decomposition for Combinatorial Optimization	TEVC	2015
R. Cheng 2015	A Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithm Using Gaussian Process-Based Inverse Modeling	TEVC	2015
M. Asafuddoula 2015	A Decomposition-Based Evolutionary Algorithm for Many Objective Optimization	TEVC	2015
K. Li 2015	An Evolutionary Many-Objective Optimization Algorithm Based on Dominance and Decomposition	TEVC	2015
H. Wang 2015	Two_Arch2: An Improved Two-Archive Algorithm for Many-Objective Optimization	TEVC	2015
H. Ishibuchi 2015	Behavior of Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithms on Many-Objective Knapsack Problems	TEVC	2015
Y. Yuan 2016	A New Dominance Relation-Based Evolutionary Algorithm for Many-Objective Optimization	TEVC	2016
Y Yuan 2016	Balancing Convergence and Diversity in Decomposition-Based Many-Objective Optimizers	TEVC	2016
X. Ma 2016	A Multiobjective Evolutionary Algorithm Based on Decision Variable Analyses for Multiobjective Optimization Problems With Large-Scale Variables	TEVC	2016
R. Wang 2016	Decomposition-Based Algorithms Using Pareto Adaptive Scalarizing Methods	TEVC	2016
R. Cheng 2016	A Reference Vector Guided Evolutionary Algorithm for Many-Objective Optimization	TEVC	2016
M. Li 2016	Pareto or Non-Pareto: Bi-Criterion Evolution in Multiobjective Optimization	TEVC	2016
PlatEMO 2017	PlatEMO: A MATLAB Platform for Evolutionary Multi-Objective Optimization	IEEE CIM	2017
H. Ishibuchi 2017	Performance of Decomposition-Based Many-Objective Algorithms Strongly Depends on Pareto Front Shapes	TEVC	2017
X. Zhang 2018	A Decision Variable Clustering-Based Evolutionary Algorithm for Large-Scale Many-Objective Optimization	TEVC	2018